

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Approach to Examining the Factors' Affecting Work Life Balance among Female Teachers': An Empirical Study

Gazi Md. Shakhawat Hossain, Md. Nayem Hossen, Md. Sharifur Rahman, &
Maruf Hasan

Abstract

The main purpose of this study is to examine the factors influencing the work-life balance of female teachers. The study population was composed of female teacher of educational institutions in Barishal division. The respondents were identified through databases from Barishal Education Board, and Ministry of Education, Bangladesh. A convenience sampling was used to recruit participants. We developed a five-point Likert-based questionnaire (ranging from 1, strongly disagree, to 5, strongly agree). For data collection, the 630 questionnaires distributed, 370 completed questionnaires were returned, yielding a response rate of 58.73%. Statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS 23.0 and AMOS 23.0. The study employing structural equation modelling (SEM) as the primary statistical technique to analyzed the relationship between dependent and independent variable. Result showed that the regression coefficient for the path from co-worker support (CS) to work-life balance (WLB) is positive ($\beta_1 = 0.681$) which indicates that CS contributes to WLB of female teachers. Similarly, the path from work overload (WO) to work-life balance (WLB) is also significant ($\beta_2 = 0.425$) which indicates that when WO decreases, work life conflict of female teachers also decreases. Likewise, the path from job engagement (JE) to work-life balance (WLB) is positive ($\beta_3 = 0.361$) which indicates that JE contributes to WLB. This study is more significant especially in the context of Bangladesh because more and more women are entering into the teaching profession as a result pattern of socio-economic status has changed. In Bangladesh, female teachers can examine their WLB issues using the factors of this study. Finally, different professionals may facilitate awareness about WLB issues confronted by women to make a favorable social attitude towards them.

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About Author

Gazi Md. Shakhawat Hossain, Masters of Business Administration (MBA), Management Science and Engineering (MSE), School of Management (SOM), Huazhong University of Science and Technology (HUST), Hubei, Wuhan, P.R. China.

Md. Nayem Hossen (Corresponding Author), CEO, NayTechs, Major M A Jalil Road, Bottola, Barisal-8200, Bangladesh.

Md. Sharifur Rahman, Lecturer, Department of Food Technology and Engineering, Faculty of Nutrition and Food Science, Patuakhali Science and Technology University, Dumki, Patuakhali - 8602, Bangladesh.

Maruf Hasan, Master of Public Administration (MPA), Administrative Management, College of Public Administration (CPA), Huazhong University of Science and Technology (HUST), Hubei, Wuhan, P.R. China.

1. Introduction

In recent years, economic, social, and cultural changes have had an impact on the working lives of individuals. In particular, the rise in living standards and the importance of work and family life have intensified the demands on individuals, on work, and on family (Darcy et al., 2012; Kuzulu, Taşdelen-Karçkay & Bakalim, 2017; Pattusamy & Jacob, 2015). The relationship between work and family life is bidirectional. Accordingly, a person's work-life can affect his/her family life, and his/her family life might also affect his/her work-life (Hill et al., 2001; Helvaci et al., 2017; Peeters et al., 2005). Because work and family roles continuously interact with one another, this concept has been handled in two different, but related ways, as work-family conflict and family-work conflict (Cinamon & Rich, 2002; Frone et al., 1997). In a national WLB benchmarking study on 284 organizations throughout Australia (Lewis et al., 2007), 75% of the surveyed organizations agreed that with WLB programs, there have been increases in employee motivation, satisfaction and engagement. 60% of the surveyed organizations agreed that through WLB programs, employees are able to better manage their work stress. On average, respondents reported a 7% reduction in turnover and a 9% reduction in absenteeism through WLB programs. On the flipside, studies have also reported that although WLB programs are available to employees, the utilization rate of these programs has been relatively low (Nord et al., 2002; Thompson et al., 1999). According to the Third European Working Conditions Survey (Paoli & Merllie', 2001), which was conducted in 15 European countries, 10% of men and women cannot fulfil their family responsibilities due to the amount of time they spend at work. In Bulgaria, Romania, and Turkey these rates are higher: 22% of men and 25% of women are unable to fulfil their family responsibilities in these countries. Most research in this area has been conducted in the fields of labor economics, human resources, and business (Helvaci et al., 2017; Taşdelen-Karçkay & Bakalim, 2017).

The nature of the workplace today is affected by different family and work-related factors. In the workforce today there are more women in general, single parent families and dual career couples compared to previous decades. Emphasis on profit and results pressures companies to extend their working hours, which interferes with family and private life of their employees. These interferences and different expectations and demand from work and life cause work life conflict. Work life conflict has consequences on employee performance, and many companies are trying to prevent it. The topic of work-family conflict has been of particular interest because recent studies have demonstrated that 40% of employed parents experience work-family conflict for at least a period of time in their lives (Allen et al., 2000). Studies show that work-family conflict and family-work conflict have a negative and significant correlation with psychological well-being (Frone et al., 1997; Hughes & Galinsky, 1994). Most of the research that analyzed work life conflict dealt mainly with demographic characteristics of participants, family factors or work life balance policies and its influence on the work life conflict. Emphasis was on the demographic characteristics and work life balance policies and macro-level variables (Nitzsche et al., 2014). A rather small number of researches has examined how organizational factors impact on work life balance of female teacher.

Bangladesh is an overpopulated and resource limited country where services and opportunities are country resource limited and overpopulated country where society is highly stratified, services and opportunities are determined by gender, class and location. However, women constitute nearly half of the total population, which indicates that women represent a huge possibility to be utilized for the development of socio-economic condition of the country. Women are economically, socially and culturally left behind in the traditional society of Bangladesh. Women are going ahead along with their counterpart. Women are contributing significantly in

private organizations, public organizations, as well as starting new ventures and running existing businesses. Kirchmeyer (2000) considers a balanced life as one in which the individual achieves satisfying experiences in all life domains. The topic of WLB issues of female teachers warrant urgent attention, studies relating to the WLB of women in Bangladesh are particularly very limited (Mathew & Panchanatham, 2011). In this perspective, the present study is a step towards analyzing the WLB issues confronted by the women teacher.

Based on the identified research gap, the specific aim was to develop and validate an appropriate instrument to evaluate the WLB policies faced by women teachers. Based on this instrument, we sought to analyze the important factors influencing the WLB of women. Also, this study sought to investigate the factors affecting the work life balance of women teachers through the following research questions:

Is there a significant relationship between the selected organizational factors and the work life balance of female teachers?

In this context, the current work is a step towards analyzing the WLB issues confronted by the women extensive literature review to identify gaps in the field of research into female teachers' WLB followed by a discussion of study's major objectives; methodology, involving various statistical analyses and the development of a psychometric instrument to measure WLB issues, findings, managerial implications and limitations. The paper concludes with ideas for future studies and a brief conclusion.

2. Literature Review

Work-life balance (WLB) refers to the maintenance of balance between work and family responsibilities so that role conflicts between them are reduced (De Cieri et al., 2005). Individuals with healthy WLB experience less stress, and show greater satisfaction with life in general compared to those with poor WLB (Hobson et al., 2001). A good work-life balance is defined as a situation in which workers feel that they are capable of balancing their work and non-work commitments. Work life balance (WLB) is the separation between work life and personal life of an employee in the organization. Workers' everyday experiences showed that work and family are both sources of growth and support as well as burdens and strains (Barnett & Hyde, 2001; Crouter, 1984). The combination of ever-increasing demands at the workplace and the demands at home are causing imbalances in work-life (Banu & Duraipandian, 2014; Singh & Shukla, 2017). WLB is advocated to achieve a more harmonious balance between their work responsibilities and their private responsibilities and personal interests and achieving balance needs to be considered from multiple perspectives (Hudson, 2005).

Work-life imbalance has been found to have various negative consequences. One of them is that, it has been found to affect the employee's family relationship to the extent that it could cause work-family conflict (Alam et al., 2009; Doble & Supriya, 2010). When the employees' family relationship is affected, it could affect their concentration at work and consequently affect their performance. Besides that, Major et al., (2002) found that longer working hours (i.e. work-life imbalance) was significantly linked to depression and stress related problems. This finding is supported by the study of Kinman and Jones (2003), which showed that long working hours has an effect on employees' psychological and physical wellbeing and both these factors are linked with job stress in many occupations. Currently, there are quite a large number of studies that have been done looking into the issue of work-life balance. Some of these studies examines factors that lead to the uptake of work-life programmes implemented by organizations (McCarthy et al., 2013), while others studied the factors affecting work-life balance (Syrek et al., 2013). Most importantly, all these studies focused on factors that could improve the work-life

balance of today's workforce, and all of them agreed that there are many factors that could influence it, and further research needs to be conducted discover other factors that could contribute to work-life balance. Hence, it is the objective of this study to fill this gap, and determine the relationship between several individual factors and organizational factors to work-life balance. Specifically, the current study focuses on the influence that job engagement, workload, and organizational support, has an impact on work-life balance. The findings of this research would contribute to existing literature on work-life balance because it helps in understanding the role played by organizational factors in enhancing the workforce work-life balance.

3. Conceptual Model and Hypothesis Development

3.1 Co-worker support (CS)

CS is concerned to support and sensitivity to fellow employees. Kirby and Krone (2002) found that positive relationship between CS and WLB. According to Suresh and Kodikal, (2017) CS is important to manage work family conflict. In relation to the relationship between CS and WLB program utilization, researchers have found CS to be related to higher program utilization (Kossek et al., 1999). Some researchers have found CS to have no influence on WLB programs utilization. Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H1: There is a significant positive relationship between CS and WLB.

3.2 Work Overload (WO)

That here are many factors that could affect WLB, WO is one of them. Virick et al., (2007) suggested that WO have a negative influence on WLB. Yildirim and Ayca (2008) found that irregular work schedules and WO were the insignificant predictors of WLB. Likewise, Schaufeli et al. (2002) and Sharma, et al. (2016) proved that WO have a significant influence on WLB. Over time work has also an impact on WLB. Therefore, it is expected that WO would be negatively and strongly related to WLB, and it is hypothesized that:

H2: There is a negative relationship between WO and WLB.

3.3 Job Engagement (JE)

JE is the state in which individuals are emotionally and intellectually committed to the organization as measured by three primary behaviours such as say, stay and strive (Susi & Jawaharrani, 2011). Moreover, Schaufeli et al. (2002) specifically define job engagement as a positive, fulfilling work-related state of mind that is characterized by dedication. Indeed, JE has a positive impact on WLB, and this premise is supported by previous research which found significant positive relationship between JE and WLB (Rich et al., 2010). This study argued that job JE could affects employees' work-life balance. There is previous study support that, there is a significant relationship between employee JE and WLB (Amarakoon & Wickramasinghe, 2010; Susi & Jawaharrani, 2011).). It is important to highlight that highly engaged employees are vigorous, dedicated and absorbed employees. When this happen, WLB could be increase. Hence, it is highly possible that a JE could positively affect WLB. In relation to that, it is hypothesized that:

H3: There is a significant positive relationship between JE and WLB.

A number of conceptual models of work life balance/work family conflict/work family enrichment have been proposed (Anafarta 2011). Traditionally, one of the most studied concepts in the work-personal life issues is work-family conflict and extensive research in WLB measurement is based on work family conflict (Carr et al. 2008). There is no blue print for any specific model of WLB in the literature and work-life balance is the key mechanism which has a

positive relationship with exogenous variables. The initial theoretical model proposed in Figure 1 is constructed by taking all the exogenous and endogenous variables. Three of the exogenous variables, namely, co-worker support (CS), work overload (WO), and job engagement (JE) are found to be positively associated with the endogenous variables.

Figure 1: Research Model

4. Methodology

The study population was composed of female teacher of educational institutions in Barishal division. The respondents were identified through databases from local governmental bodies, and Barishal Education Board, Ministry of Education. A total of 650 teachers belonging to the various educational institutions and, were contacted personally with them to participate in the survey. In line with prior studies, we developed a five-point Likert-based questionnaire (ranging from 1, strongly disagree, to 5, strongly agree). Of the 630 questionnaires distributed, 370 completed questionnaires were returned, yielding a response rate of 58.73%. A convenience sampling was used to recruit participants. The distribution and collection of the survey instruments took about two months. In the preliminary stage of the study, the questionnaire was pre-tested on 30 teachers, in the period between 21 January and 30 March 2019, to validate the scale in the questionnaire. The teachers who participated in the questionnaire's pre-test phase were not included in the final sample. The questionnaire, submitted in 1st April 2019, allowed us to code 15 response variables concerning the aforementioned personal data and four logical constructs: OS; CS; JE; and WO. Some of the returned questionnaire was incomplete that was exclude from the final data set. After the teachers' responses to the questionnaires were codified, quantitative analyses were carried out on the data set. Collected data was analysed by descriptive statistical methods such as frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) technique was performed to establish relationship between various predictors with WLB.

5. Data Analysis

5.1 Demographic Description of Respondents

Table1 summarizes the information about the demographic variables of age, education, and marital status of the respondents. A total of 290 female teachers took part in the study. The sample's age range varied from 25 to 51 and above years of old. Moreover, 85 (29.31%) percent of respondents were belonged to 25 to 30 years of age group, 105 (36.21%) percent of them belonged to 31 to 40 years of age group, 52 (17.93%) percent of participants belonged to 41 to 50 years of age group, and 48 (16.55%) percent of them were above 50 years of age.

Table 1 also shows that, 77 (26.55%) had obtained higher secondary certificate, 53 (18.28%) have got graduate certificate, and 119 (41.03%) were qualified with post-graduation, and very

few of them was more than post graduate. The results also reveal that more than 70% of the respondents are married. Distribution of respondents Age, Education, and Marital Status are shown in Figure 2.

Table -1: Demographic Description of Sample

Variable	Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age	25-30 Years	85	29.31
	31-40 Years	105	36.21
	41-50 Years	52	17.93
	51 and Above	48	16.55
Educational Qualification	Higher Secondary	77	26.55
	Bachelor	53	18.28
	Masters	119	41.03
	Others	41	14.14
Marital Status	Single	80	27.59
	Married	210	72.41

5.2 Investigating Univariate-Normality Test of Constructs

The statistical techniques of testing normality are sensitive to the research data, as a result, it is recommended to check the histogram with the values of skewness and kurtosis to evaluate univariate normality. In this study, visual assessment of the data distribution of all constructs demonstrated that the shapes of all univariate distributions were acceptable. Additionally, the findings in Table 2 indicate that all values of the variables were within the accepted range of skewness and kurtosis.

Figure 2: Distribution of respondents Age, Education, and Marital Status

Table 2: Skewness and Kurtosis Statistics for the study variables

Scale	Skewness	Kurtosis
Co-workers Support (CS)	-.338	-1.027
Work Overload (WO)	-.427	-.687
Job Engagement (JE)	-.521	-.599
Work Life Balance (WLB)	-.606	-.633

5.3 Reliability Analysis

Reliability is the degree to which measures are free from random error and therefore yield consistent results. To prove that, the reliability coefficient was run on SPSS for each set of constructs and the results are presented in Table 3, which shows the Cronbach's alpha (α) value for each variable. The result of this analysis shows that all of the constructs got high reliability

and more than 0.80. Cronbach's value result varied between 0.804 and 0.918.

Table 3: Results of the Cronbach's alpha (α)

Scale	Co-workers Support (CS)	Work Overload (WO)	Job Engagement (JE)	Work Life Balance (WLB)
No. of Items	4	4	4	3
Cronbach's alpha (α)	0.903	0.887	0.804	0.918

Overall, the result shows that all alpha values (α) of the study instruments are reliable and exhibit appropriate construct reliability. Constructs exceeded the suggested level of 0.7 (Drost, 2011) for Cronbach's coefficient alpha, indicating acceptable levels for the reliability of constructs.

5.4 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

The main objective of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) is to assess the construct validity of the proposed measurement model (Hair et al., 2014). Assessing construct validity using the CFA involved an assessment of the convergent validity and the discriminant validity.

5.4.1 Convergent Validity

The measurement model for this study is presented in Table 4. According to Hulland (1999) there are three step procedures for evaluating the measurement model namely, individual item reliabilities, convergent validity and discriminant validity. Individual item reliabilities are determined based on item loading, and it is recommended that all items have loadings between 0.5 and 1.0, and that items with loadings below 0.50 be dropped from the analysis (Hair et al., 2014; Hulland, 1999). Convergent validity refers to the extent to which item truly represents the intended latent construct and indeed correlate with other measures of the same latent construct (Hair et al., 2014). According to Fornell and Larcker, (1981), convergent validity was assessed by examining the average variance extracted (AVE) and composite reliability (CR) of 0.70. Chin (1998) recommends that AVE of more than 0.5 and the CR of 0.7 or above are deemed acceptable.

Table 4: Results of the Measurement Model

Constructs	Items	Loadings	CR	AVE
Co-workers Support (CS)	CS-1	0.933	0.948	0.820
	CS-2	0.890		
	CS-3	0.901		
	PE-4	0.898		
Work Overload (WO)	WO-1	0.954	0.935	0.784
	WO-2	0.921		
	WO-3	0.856		
	WO-4	0.804		
Job Engagement (JE)	JE-1	0.889	0.944	0.810
	JE-2	0.901		
	JE-3	0.947		
	JE-4	0.860		
Work Life Balance (WLB)	WLB-1	0.903	0.916	0.784
	WLB-2	0.911		
	WLB-3	0.840		

As shown in Table, all item loads a range from 0.804 to 0.954 into their respective construct. Also be seen from Table 4, all AVE are above 0.5 and the composite reliability values are more than 0.7. Therefore, it can be concluded that convergent validity has been established.

5.4.2 Discriminant Validity

To address discriminant validity, the square root of the AVE is compared against the correlations of the other constructs, when the AVE extracted is greater than its correlations with all the other constructs, the discriminant validity has been established (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), and this is shown in Table 5. The discriminant validity, construct is truly distinct from other constructs (Duarte & Raposo, 2010). As shown in Table 5, all squares roots of the AVEs (diagonal cells) are higher than the correlations between constructs and that definitely confirms adequate discriminant validity.

Table 5. Discriminant Validity of Construct

Constructs	1	2	3	4
1 Co-workers Support (CS)	0.906			
2 Work Overload (WO)	-0.033	0.885		
3 Job Engagement (JE)	0.205	-0.082	0.900	
4 Work Life Balance (WLB)	0.148	0.450	0.685	0.885

5.5 Testing of the Hypothesis of the Structural Model

The structural model represents the relationship between constructs or latent variables that were hypothesized in the research model. The goodness of the theoretical model is established by the variance of the endogenous constructs and the significance of all path estimates (Chin, 2010). The results of the structural model from the SPSS output are shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Results of the Structural Model

Hypothesis	Relationship of Path		β -value	t--value	p-value	Finings
	IV	Path DV				
H ₁	CS	---> WLB	0.681	8.271	0.000**	Supported
H ₂	WO	---> WLB	0.425	6.326	0.000**	Supported
H ₃	JE	---> WLB	0.361	3.987	0.000**	Supported

CS was found positively and significantly related to WLB ($\beta = 0.681$, $t = 8.271$, $p < 0.05$), thus supporting H₁. In addition, WO ($\beta = 0.425$, $t = 6.326$, $p < 0.05$), and JE ($\beta = 0.361$, $t = 3.987$, $p < 0.05$) were found positively and significantly related to WLB. Therefore, H₁, H₂, and H₃ were supported.

5.5.1 Structural Model

After achieving the satisfactory fit of the measurement model, a structural model is to be tested. The structural model aims to specify which variable directly or indirectly influence the values of other variables in the model. Hence, the purpose of the structural model is to test the underlying hypotheses. As mentioned in Table 6, the hypotheses are presented in three causal paths to determine the relationships between the variables under consideration. The structural model shown in Figure 3.

The results presented in Table 6 indicate that the hypotheses H₁, H₂, and H₃ are statistically significant. Thus, these hypotheses are supported. Since, there is significant relationship established in the hypothesized direction. The regression coefficient for the path from CS to WLB is positive ($\beta_1 = 0.681$) which indicates that CS contributes to WLB of female teachers. Similarly, the path from WO to WLB is positive ($\beta_2 = 0.425$) which indicates that when WO decreases, satisfaction with WLB raise; WO increases, satisfaction with WLB declines simultaneously. There is an adverse relationship between WO an WLB. The employer recognizes that staff may need to

change hours, require special leave or other forms of support to enable them to do this properly. Employers are willing to support this because they recognize that the key benefit is improved effectiveness at work. Studies carried out show that continuous work demands create stress. Likewise, the path from JE to WLB is positive ($\beta = 0.361$) which indicates that JE contributes to WLB.

Figure 3: Structural Model

5.6 Goodness of Fit Statistics

To evaluate the structural model, goodness-of-fit indices are examined to assess if the hypothesized structural model fits the data. The results of the goodness of fit are presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Goodness of Fit Statistics

Name of Index	Value	Level of Acceptance	Meet Acceptance?
X ² /df	2.071	between 1.00 and 3.00	Yes
GFI	0.958	0.90 or, greater	Yes
RMSEA	0.086	between 0.050 and 0.080	Slightly
AGFI	0.899	0.90 or, greater	Yes
TLI	0.940	0.90 or, greater	Yes
NFI	0.915	0.90 or, greater	Yes
CFI	0.904	0.90 or, greater	Yes

Note: X²/df = Normed Chi-square (Parsimonious fit indices), GFI = Goodness of Fit (Absolute fit indices), RMSEA = Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (Absolute fit indices), AGFI = Adjusted Goodness of Fit (Incremental fit indices), TLI = Tucker-Lewis Index (Incremental indices), NFI = Normed Fit (Incremental fit), CFI = Comparative (Incremental fit)

While RMSEA is slightly over the threshold of 0.08 (MacCallum & Browne, 1993 suggest a value of up to 1.0), other indices are within the recommended threshold levels, indicating an acceptable fit. The indices for goodness-of-fit demonstrate that this model fits the data adequately.

6. Discussions

The main purpose of this study is to determine the influence of organizational factors i.e. co-worker support, work overload, and job engagement on female teachers work-life balance. As discussed in the literature review section, all these variables have previously been linked to WLB either empirically and/or theoretically. In general, the findings of this study support previous findings, except the finding regarding to work overload. The findings relating to co-worker support, work overload, and job engagement are as hypothesized, it shows that there is relationship between CS and WLB; WO and WLB; and JE an WLB. Hence, let's examine this finding gradually. In essence, the findings implied that CS was found to have a positive effect on WLB. In organization, supportive employees mean that the co-workers value the contribution of

their employees and cares for their wellbeing (Eisenberger et al., 1986). Co-workers understand the needs of colleague, inside and outside the organization, and therefore providing the support that they need to succeed on the job and in life. One factor is not good for WLB that is WO. With regard to workload, studies have repeatedly emphasized that excessive work overload or work overload is detrimental to WLB. The findings of the study also revealed that JE and WLB were positively related. It seemed that the findings of this study confirm the findings of previous research (Amarakoon, & Wickramasinghe, 2010; Susi & Jawaharrani, 2011). In other words, job engagement is important for work-life balance. Indeed, when people are highly engaged with their job, they are able to do their job better and thus is able to experience higher WLB. This implies that organizations must ensure that employees are engaged in their job, so that they become efficient at performing them, and thus they can achieve WLB.

7. Conclusion

The present study incorporates the results of an empirical analysis of the WLB issues faced by the female teachers. A psychometric tool was developed based on preliminary qualitative research, and a literature survey to measure the WLB issues of these teachers. Using 15 items, three factors, a five-point scale, and a convenient sampling survey of the WLB issues of women was conducted. Standard statistical processing of the generated data revealed a number of issues related to WLB, including the fact that female teachers struggle to highly demanding organizational task and duties. The prominent WLB issues that they face are work overload, health maintenance problems, and time management. The complexity of these issues poses very specific demands on the individual's role system. As the work roles of female teachers and their personal and familial roles quite often contradict each other, these women struggle to strike a balance between work and personal life. As a result, work-life imbalances and conflict have become a common feature of the lives of many aspiring female teachers. In addition, CS, moderate WO, and JE are good for enhancing teachers WLB, which implies that organizations must do something to enhance these three factors. In addition, this study supports the fact that low level of workload is important in the workplace, but excessive workload can be detrimental to teachers WLB. This means organizations must monitor these three factors so that it could benefit their organizations and not do any harm to the WLB of female teachers. This study is important especially in the context of Bangladesh because more and more women are entering into the teaching profession as a result pattern of socio-economic status has changed. In Bangladesh, female teachers can examine their WLB issues using the factors of this study. Human resource management professionals, management consultants, and policy makers may also use this scale to level out the issues of WLB among women entrepreneurs. Finally, different professionals may facilitate awareness about WLB issues confronted by women to make a favorable social attitude towards them.

8. Limitations and Suggestions for Future Research

As the prevailing roles of women in the family and society are comparable to those of many other countries. In direction this research could help international policymakers and organizations to design more coherent and internationally applicable policies towards women in the different sector. Some limitations to this study should be addressed. One of the limitations of this study is also connected with the proposed research models. Predictors and consequences of work life conflict are then drawn from already published work. Future research might put a light on some different variables when exploring predictors and consequences of work life conflict that were not investigated by previous research. Secondly, the data were obtained only from the population who lived in city. Generalization of the results is limited to and may be not representative for all of the teachers since participants were reached with a use of convenient

technique. To address this, future studies could examine a more diverse sample obtained from different cities and international populations as a way of evaluating the WLB Scale's.

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